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Research Trends and Challenges among Postgraduate Linguistics Students in South Punjab Universities

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Abstract

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This study investigates research trends among postgraduate students in South Punjabi universities' English (Linguistics) departments. The main purpose of this study is to examine students' research areas, approaches, difficulties, and motivations. The 50 postgraduate students were given a structured questionnaire to complete as part of a quantitative research design. SPSS was used to analyse the data and to analyse descriptive and inferential statistical methods. The results show that stylistics and computational linguistics receive comparatively less attention; the majority of postgraduate students concentrate on disciplines like English Language Teaching (ELT), sociolinguistics, and discourse analysis. The study also highlights major challenges that students come across, such as restricted access to research materials, a lack of academic assistance, trouble getting to create research questions, and problems with time management. The findings have important practical implications, suggesting that universities should enhance access to digital research resources, provide regular training in research methodology, and strengthen supervisory support systems. The study contributes theoretically by offering region-specific empirical insights into postgraduate research trends in applied linguistics, particularly in under-researched contexts such as South Punjab. The results indicate that universities need to enhance access to digital research materials and offer enhanced supervisory support. They are also supposed to provide organised research training to enhance the quality of postgraduate research in linguistics.

Keywords: Inferential statistics, Postgraduate students, Pakistan's South Punjab region, Research Trends

Introduction

Postgraduate research is an important part of university education because it helps students develop new ideas and add to knowledge in their field. In the field of linguistics, postgraduate students study how language is used, how people communicate, and how language can be taught in a better way. Recent research shows that students in applied linguistics are now choosing many different and practical topics that relate to real-life situations (Yahya, Arif, & Awan, 2023). This change is also taking place in Pakistan, where linguistics and English departments are conducting more research (Ghulam et al., 2025). The support that postgraduate students receive from their supervisors is important to their success. Students who receive good supervision are better able to comprehend research techniques, write well, and complete their studies on schedule (Grant, Hackney, & Edgar, 2014). Many Pakistani students continue to struggle with issues like poor research guidance, difficulty in academic writing, and restricted access to journals (Kanwal, Shahnaz, & Gulzar, 2022; Irfan, Khan, & Zeeshan, 2023). Their research choices or the quality of their work are impacted by these issues. Pakistani students are now showing a keen interest in subjects like discourse analysis, sociolinguistics, and second language acquisition. These subjects enable them to investigate societal, identity, and educational issues (Sattar, Farooq, & Khalil, 2024). As language technology becomes more significant in the world, some students are also starting to work in new fields like computational linguistics, corpus linguistics, and NLP (Yaseen et al., 2025). The development of these fields is dependent upon the availability of resources, which are still limited in many universities.

According to the recent findings in the field of applied linguistics, the trends in research are constantly changing because of the global academic and technological processes. Research in applied linguistics is becoming more interdisciplinary, as scholars have noted that there is more attention to real-world language matters and data-driven methods (Lei and Liu,

2019; Liu and Hu, 2024). The implementation of superior analytical tools like topic modelling has allowed scholars to gain a clearer insight into the new tendencies and changes in the field of research (Hong et al., 2020). These changes show that postgraduate students should be prepared with the latest research skills in order to be able to meet the world's academic standards.

The quality of the postgraduate research is greatly associated with the research experience and the academic environment offered to the students by universities. Research training, the availability of learning resources, and participation in research-oriented learning activities play a great role in improving the capacity of students to perform meaningful research (Daniel, 2022; Brew, 2018). The trends in higher education worldwide are based on the necessity to create research-centred institutions that facilitate innovation, cooperation, and knowledge creation (Altbach and Salmi, 2020; Maringe and Osman, 2016). The factors are important in developing the research abilities of postgraduate students.

Another important variable that determines the outcome of postgraduate research is supervisory relationships. Effective and positive supervision assists students to think critically, write their academic papers effectively and accomplish their research in a very efficient way. Nevertheless, poor supervisory behaviour may cause confusion, delays, and a decrease in the quality of research (Singh, 2022). Supervision is regarded as a primary component of doctoral and postgraduate training in the higher education context because it has a direct influence on the academic growth of students and the volume of research work (Kehm, 2021; Tight, 2020).

Several studies have been reported in Pakistan about the issues surrounding the postgraduate research practices, especially in the public sector universities. Poor research facilities, inaccessibility to journals, and unorganised research training remain a problem and still influence the performance of

the students (Ahmed, 2023; Malik, 2021). Supervisory issues, such as insufficient feedback and academic support, also make the research process more complicated (Khan, 2022). Academic writing and language proficiency are also troublesome to the students, which may interfere with their capability to write high-quality research (Hussain, 2019; Iqbal, 2020).

These international and national trends underscore the need to study the trends in postgraduate research within particular regional settings. The insights into the way students choose the topics of their research, implement the methods, and address the difficulties can be useful to enhance the culture of research and academic practices. It is important to investigate these points in those areas that are under-researched, like South Punjab, where the institutional constraints and the state of academic affairs can have a profound impact on the research experience of students.

These trends make it crucial to research the subjects, approaches, and difficulties as experienced by the postgraduate students. This helps universities improve their research training and supervision (Siddiqui et al., 2024). In this connection, only a small number of studies have explored postgraduate research in English (Linguistics) departments of the Universities of South Punjab because this region faces some academic challenges.

The present study examines the research trends of postgraduate students in the Department of English (Linguistics) in South Punjab. It looks at their research areas, methods, challenges, and motivations. Understanding these trends can help improve supervision, build better research skills, and strengthen the research culture in these universities.

There is a lot of research on postgraduate studies and applied linguistics; very few studies have focused on research trends among postgraduate students in English (Linguistics) departments in South Punjab. Mostly research papers only discuss research problems or specific areas; this research aims to fill the gap by providing a complete and region-based analysis

of research trends, methods, and challenges in South Punjab.

Key Objectives

1. To identify the current research trends and major areas of focus among postgraduate students in the Department of English (Linguistics) at the University of South Punjab.
2. To examine the challenges and factors that influence postgraduate students' research choices and progress in the field of linguistics.

Research Questions

1. Q1. What are the main research trends and focus areas among postgraduate students in the Department of English (Linguistics) at the University of South Punjab?
2. Q2. What challenges and influencing factors affect postgraduate students' research selection, progress, and outcomes in linguistics?

Research Gap

Many studies have been conducted on postgraduate research and applied linguistics; very few studies have focused specifically on South Punjab. The previous research has mostly been conducted on a larger national or global scale, and the specific academic situation in this region has not been studied in detail. Previous research tends to concentrate on a single area, i.e., research topics, supervision, or challenges. No studies have been found that analysed research trends, methodologies, and challenges in a single study. The proposed research will help address this gap by offering a detailed and area-based study of postgraduate research practices in English (Linguistics) departments in South Punjab.

Literature Review

Research Trends in Applied Linguistics

According to Yahya, Arif, and Awan (2023), a lot of applied linguistics researchers choose practical subjects that address social language patterns, communication, and classroom problems. According to Lei and Liu (2019), postgraduate students in linguistics departments are becoming more interested in

research and are focusing on subjects that represent everyday communication issues and local language needs. This demonstrates how postgraduate research is shifting toward more relevant and context-based fields of study. These studies point out the increasingly practical and contextual research in applied linguistics; they do not directly relate how these tendencies manifest in regional settings like South Punjab. It is necessary to look at the question of whether postgraduate students in this area pursue the same tendencies or have their own preferences in research.

Recent international research also confirms that the research in applied linguistics is becoming more dynamic and interdisciplinary. Researchers have noted that technological progress, data-driven models, and the necessity to overcome real-life communication issues are becoming current tendencies in research (Liu and Hu, 2024; Hong et al., 2020). This trend has prompted postgraduate students to think and write more about practical and socially-oriented problems.

Role of Supervision in Postgraduate Research

The quality of postgraduate research is significantly influenced by supervision and feedback. Students who receive effective guidance are better able to understand research methods, complete assignments on time, and develop their academic writing abilities. Experiences with supervision are frequently uneven, according to a number of Pakistani studies. While many postgraduate students experience delays and unclear instructions from supervisors, Liaqat (2021) discovered that some receive helpful, timely support. Riaz, Ashraf, and Butt (2020) found a significant correlation between the quality of supervision and student satisfaction, pointing out that good supervisory techniques result in improved research outcomes and increased student confidence. Past literature highlights the significance of supervision, and the research lacks empirical data that would explore the role of supervisory practices in determining the research decisions and advancements among postgraduate

research students in South Punjab.

Supervision is also important in determining academic confidence and identity of research among students. This research indicates that a positive supervisory relationship encourages critical thinking and improves the students' capacity to engage critically with the research subjects (Singh, 2022). Studies in higher education show that inconsistent supervision practices may lead to inequality in student achievement and research quality (Kehm, 2021; Tight, 2020). This highlights the importance of organised and responsible supervision mechanisms, especially where the students are highly dependent on the supervisors in providing academic guidance.

Emerging Fields in Linguistics

The choice of research topics and the development of new linguistic subfields represent another significant area in the literature. According to recent studies, postgraduate students in Pakistan are starting to investigate more specialised fields like language technology and computational linguistics. Although these fields still need improved research infrastructure and training, Liaqat (2021) noted that interest in corpus-based studies, machine learning applications, and natural language processing has grown. A lot of postgraduate theses still concentrate on regional linguistic problems, difficulties in learning English, and the distinctive characteristics of Pakistani English, which reflect local requirements and sociolinguistic contexts.

These results indicate a progressive move towards the emerging and technology-based areas, but it is not clear how far students in regions with limited resources can reach such areas. This paper explores the existence of similar patterns among postgraduate students in South Punjab.

Global academic and technological trends are also closely connected with the emergence of new subfields in linguistics. Studies have revealed that fields like computational linguistics, corpus analysis, and language

technology are becoming significant in modern applied linguistics (Lei and Liu, 2019). Such changes can be seen as a reflection of a larger shift in the field of higher education, where innovation and interdisciplinary research are becoming more promoted (Altbach and Salmi, 2020).

Challenges in Postgraduate Research

Even with these encouraging developments, postgraduate linguistics research in Pakistan still faces a number of challenges. Research progress is frequently slowed down by a lack of funding, traditional supervisory models, limited access to digital libraries, and discrepancies between students' research interests and institutional support. To improve the research culture in Pakistani universities, several studies suggest updating the supervision procedures, expanding access to journals and online resources, and enhancing research training (Siddiqui et al., 2024). According to the literature, increasing the quality and completion rate of postgraduate research requires regular reviews of research direction, topic relevance, and academic resources. These issues are common in the literature; there is a gap in the literature whereby studies are not done on a large scale, where research areas, research methods, and challenges are studied in a single regional setting.

The problems of postgraduate students are not just personal but also institutional. The research carried out in Pakistani universities shows that a research infrastructure, the absence of funding sources, and insufficient academic support impact the research development of students considerably (Ahmed, 2023; Malik, 2021). Academic writing and language proficiency have been the ongoing challenges, especially among students working in English as a second language (Hussain, 2019; Iqbal, 2020).

The literature reviewed provides significant advances in the direction of research, supervision, emerging issues, and challenges in postgraduate research in linguistics. These aspects are usually studied separately and are generally investigated on a larger national or

global level. The literature offers an integrated and region-specific study of the postgraduate research practices, especially in South Punjab, which is limited. This gap needs to be addressed by the current research, as it will investigate the areas of research, research methods, and research problems in this particular context.

Research Methodology

Research Design

A quantitative research design was used in this study to investigate the research trends among postgraduate students in the English (Linguistics) Departments of universities in South Punjab.

Population and Sample

The population of the current study consisted of postgraduate students pursuing English (Linguistics) programs in Bahauddin Zakariya University, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur, and Ghazi University, South Punjab. A convenience sample of 50 students was taken out of this population, which included M.A., M.Phil. and PhD students. This sampling technique was suitable as the participants who were willing to participate in the study were easily approached. The research has certain limitations. Convenience sampling and small sample size can be a limitation to the external validity of the results for all postgraduate students in South Punjab or other areas.

Research Instrument

The primary instrument of data collection was a structured questionnaire. It was separated into seven parts, which included demographic data, study programs, thesis topics, areas of research, areas of interest, motivations for conducting research and prospective research directions. Some closed-ended and open-ended questions were incorporated to give specific information. Field experts reviewed the questionnaire to make sure that it was content-valid and clear when it was distributed to the participants.

Data Collection Procedure

The data were obtained online. Participants

were told the purpose of the study and assured that their answers would be kept private. This was all voluntary, and the students could skip whatever question they did not want to answer.

Data Analysis

The data were collected and then entered into the SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 25 for analysis. Descriptive and Inferential statistics were analysed through SPSS.

Results and Data Analysis

The data were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages, and inferential statistics to identify major trends in research areas, methodologies, and challenges faced by students.

Table 1. Research Orientation and Methodology

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Selected Research Topic	Yes	40	80%
	No	10	20%
Topic Aligned with Current Trends	Yes	35	70%
	No	15	30%
Research Methodology	Qualitative	22	44%
	Quantitative	12	24%
	Mixed Methods	16	32%

Table 1 indicates that the majority of the postgraduate students (80%) had already chosen their research topics, which is an indication that they were already undertaking their research work. Another significant percentage (70%) also indicated that their studies were in line with the current trends in the study of linguistics, which implies that students are aware of the modern trends in research. When it came to methodology, 44% of students adopted qualitative methods, while 32% chose mixed methods, and 24% showed propensity towards quantitative methods. In this trend, qualitative and mixed-method designs are prevalent among researchers in the field of linguistics, as this is what linguistic research entails, as it may need interpretation, context, and perception of

human interaction.

Table 2. Research Fields and Challenges

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Field of Research	Sociolinguistics	15	30%
	Discourse Analysis	10	20%
	Second Language Acquisition	8	16%
	Psycholinguistics	6	12%
	Computational Linguistics	4	8%
	Pragmatics	3	6%
	Other	4	8%
Main Challenges	Access to Resources	14	28%
	Lack of Academic Support	10	20%
	Time Management	8	16%
	Framing Research Questions	8	16%
	Language Barriers	6	12%
	Other	4	8%

Table 2 indicates that Sociolinguistics was the major research field of most students (30%), Discourse Analysis (20%), and Second Language Acquisition (16%). It can also be said that lots of students are keen on learning about the working of language in society and communication. A smaller number of students were choosing Psycholinguistics (12%), Computational Linguistics (8%), and Pragmatics (6%), and this may indicate that technical and cognitive domains are not investigated frequently. It is also observed in the table that the greatest difficulty encountered by the students was the lack of research resources (28%), which was followed by the absence of academic support (20%). The time management issues (16%), formulating research questions (16%), and language barriers (12) also became a problem among some students. These findings indicate that although students have the motivation to undertake research, universities continue to

play a bigger role in assisting them, regarding materials, supervision, and direction.

Table 3 Research Interests and Future Directions

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Primary Reason for Topic Choice	Personal Interest	20	40%
	Career Opportunities	12	24%
	Faculty Influence	8	16%
	Global Research Trends	6	12%
	Academic Requirement	4	8%
	University Support Needed	Access to Research Journals	16
Research Methodology Workshops		12	24%
Better Supervision		10	20%
Funding Opportunities		8	16%
Other		4	8%

Table 3 emphasises the reasons why students chose their research topics as well as the institutional support they believe they need in order to enhance their research experience. The results reveal that personal interest is the most dominant factor (40%), which means that students are mostly motivated by their personal academic interest and likes when selecting research topics. This is then followed by career opportunities (24%), meaning that future work opportunities also play a great role in their choices. Faculty influence (16) and global research trends (12) are moderate contributors,

indicating the influence of supervisors and awareness of international developments, and academic requirements (8) seem to have the least impact. Regarding support, most of the students pointed out the necessity to have access to research journals (32%), which is a significant discrepancy in research materials. Also, workshops on research methods (24) were highly demanded, which implies that skills have to be developed and things have to be trained practically. Other types of support were also noted, with a small percentage (8%), but better supervision (20%) and funding opportunities (16%) were also considered important. The majority of students have chosen their field of research according to their personal interests or career appropriateness and have become increasingly motivated and aware of the use of linguistic research. Most respondents proposed that the accessibility of research journals and workshops should be enhanced in the universities, which would allow increasing the level of research competence and the quality of research output.

Inferential Analysis

Inferential statistical analysis was conducted to examine relationships between selected demographic variables and research-related factors among postgraduate students of English (Linguistics) in South Punjab. The variables were categorical in nature; chi-square tests of independence were employed to determine whether statistically significant associations existed between variables. The level of significance was set at $p < .05$.

Chi-Square Tests

Association between Degree Program and Research Methodology

A Chi-square test of independence was conducted to examine whether postgraduate students' choice of research methodology differed according to their degree program.

Table 4. Relationship between Degree Program and Research Methodology

Test	Value	df	Sig. (p-value)
Pearson Chi-	2.356	2	0.308

Test	Value	df	Sig. (p-value)
Square			

The results revealed no statistically significant association between degree program and research methodology, $\chi^2 (2, N = 43) = 2.36$, $p = .308$. This indicates that students enrolled in different academic programs, such as M.Phil. and PhD, tend to adopt similar research methodologies. The finding suggests that methodological preferences in linguistics research are influenced more by disciplinary norms and supervisory guidance than by degree level.

Association between the University and the Field of Linguistics

To investigate whether postgraduate students' selection of research fields varied across universities, a Chi-square test of independence was performed.

Table 5. Relationship between the University and the Field of Linguistics

Test	Value	df	Sig. (p-value)
Pearson Chi-Square	36.84	20	0.012

$p = .012 < .05$

The results revealed a statistically significant association between university and research field, $\chi^2 (20, N = 50) = 36.84$, $p = .012$. This suggests that postgraduate students' choices of research areas differ greatly between South Punjab universities. Students' research choices may be influenced by institutional factors like departmental priorities, faculty expertise, and available resources, according to the strong correlation between university and research field. This suggests that different universities have different research environments, which can influence scholarly interests and research directions.

Association between Degree Program and Research Challenges

A Chi-square test was conducted to examine the relationship between the degree program and the types of research challenges faced by postgraduate students.

Table 6. Relationship between Degree Program and Research Challenges

Test	Value	df	Sig. (p-value)
Pearson Chi-Square	24.46	6	0.000

($p < .001$)

The relationship between postgraduate students' research challenges and degree programs was investigated using a Chi-square test of independence. The degree program and research challenges were found to be statistically significantly correlated ($\chi^2 (6, N = 50) = 24.46$, $p < .001$). This suggests that students face a wide range of research challenges depending on their academic level. Differences in academic requirements, research difficulty, and supervisory demands at every phase may be the cause of the variation in research challenges among degree programs.

Association between Year of Study and Topic Selection Status

To determine whether students' probability of having selected a thesis topic varied by year of study, a Chi-square test of independence was conducted.

Table 7. Relationship between Year of Study and Topic Selection Status

Test	Value	df	Sig. (p-value)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.72	2	0.001

The results revealed a statistically significant association between year of study and topic selection, $\chi^2 (2, N = 50) = 14.72$, $p = .001$. This indicates that students' probability of having selected a research topic increases significantly as they progress in their academic program. Students at more advanced stages of their academic programs are more likely to have chosen their research topics, according to the significant correlation between year of study and topic selection status. This result is expected because students usually decide on their research topics as they advance through degree requirements and develop a greater understanding of their field. It suggests early-stage students might need more direction and assistance when choosing a topic. This emphasises the significance of quick supervision and organised research orientation in the early phases of postgraduate programs to

enable easier research advancement.

The findings suggest that the majority of postgraduate students are involved in research regularly, with a preference towards qualitative and mixed-method studies. The most popular research areas were sociolinguistics and discourse analysis, whereas the lack of available resources and academic support was defined as the primary issue. These results form the basis of further interpretation in the discussion section.

Discussion

Main Findings

The results revealed that most postgraduate students in the Departments of English (Linguistics) at universities in South Punjab were actively involved in research, particularly at the M.Phil, while many were still in the early phase of their research work. The obvious choice of English both as a medium of instruction and a full-time study status reflects a scholarly atmosphere focused on research work. The majority of the respondents had already selected their topics, and they thought that their topic was in line with current trends in linguistics; this is also consistent with other recent bibliometric and content-analysis research that describes increased student interest in applied and context-sensitive linguistics in Pakistan and other parts of the region (Yanhua, 2024).

Methodological Trends

The methodological preferences among students were oriented towards qualitative and mixed-method approaches, and the former is the most numerous category, while the latter demonstrates a significant increase. This aligns with broader trends in applied linguistics, with scholars moving more towards the integration of qualitative understanding and quantitative data in seeking to resolve sophisticated language issues. Recent reviews record a gradual increase in the well-reported mixed-methods studies in applied linguistics (Yanhua, 2024).

Research Field Trends

The topics of interest are socially oriented subfields, sociolinguistics and discourse analysis, then second language acquisition and psycholinguistics, which indicates that the

students are focusing on the areas where language is related to society, identity and education. Similar findings are observed in local surveys of linguistic theses and research in Pakistani universities, with the shift towards sociolinguistic and pedagogical interests, which are directly related to the local problems and the practical value of the field (Lui & Liu, 2019).

Research Challenges

The most common issues reported were limited access to research resources, lack of academic support, difficulties in managing time, and problems in formulating research questions. These findings match recent studies on higher education in Pakistan, which highlight resource gaps, poor infrastructure, and inconsistent supervision as major obstacles to completing high-quality postgraduate research on time (Haq & Shahzad, 2021).

Supervision Issues

Supervision is another important variable: when students receive sufficient and timely guidance, they report better progress and a stronger alignment with current research trends. Inconsistent supervisory support leads to delays and reduced confidence. Both international and Pakistani studies also focus on the key role of effective supervision in the success of doctoral and master's programs, and recent suggestions of locally adapted supervisory models can enhance the mentoring practice in Pakistani society (Mahesar, 2020). The results show that postgraduate students are actively engaged in research. Universities should provide easier access to current resources, more training in research methods, and better support for supervisors to help students produce higher-quality research, as recent studies have shown that these steps improve postgraduate research outcomes (Yanhua, 2024; Haq & Shahzad, 2021).

Supervisory practices have continued to be a very important aspect that determines the advancement of research and the general satisfaction of students. Proper supervision not only helps students to choose the right research topics but also assists them in making decisions

on methods to use and writing academic papers. Past studies show that positive supervisory relationships help to increase the completion rates and the quality of the research, whereas weak supervision may have adverse effects on student motivation and performance (Singh, 2022; Kehm, 2021). That indicates that universities ought to invest in training and mentoring supervisors to enhance mentoring practices.

Institutional Implications

This research has implications for the general trends in applied linguistics research across the world as well, with a growing trend toward interdisciplinary and data-driven methods. Research studies have revealed that the latest trends in research are characterised by the combination of technology, corpus-based research, and real-life communication problems (Lei and Liu, 2019; Liu and Hu, 2024). This shows that the postgraduate students in South Punjab are gradually moving towards international research directions, but their exposure to advanced tools and digital resources can limit their involvement in the new directions.

The other significance of this study is the influence of the research environment on determining the academic experiences of students. Researchers are more likely to be competent when they have been trained on research in a structured way, have access to digital libraries and have a chance of learning together. Learning methods that are based on research have been discovered to have a considerable positive effect on the critical thinking and independent research abilities of students (Brew, 2018; Daniel, 2022).

The difference in research issues among students also indicates institutional problems in institutions of higher learning. Higher education research in the world highlights the fact that unequal access to academic opportunities and support systems may introduce differences in the quality and productivity of research (Altbach and Salmi, 2020; Maringe and Osman, 2016). These inequalities could be even more acute in the surroundings of South Punjab because of the

regional constraints and the necessity of specific policy interventions and institutional changes to benefit postgraduate researchers.

The results of this paper highlight the significance of balancing postgraduate research to meet the local requirements as well as international scholarly requirements. Students are highly interested in socially applicable issues like sociolinguistics and language education; it is necessary to promote the investigation of underexplored and new areas. The research in higher education also emphasises the need to constantly revise the priorities of research and adjust to the evolving academic environment (Tight, 2020). The quality and overall impact of postgraduate research in the field of linguistics can be improved by encouraging innovation, interdisciplinary research and international cooperation.

Conclusion

The research is a valuable source of information concerning trends in postgraduate research in English (Linguistics) departments in South Punjab. It shows that students become more interested in applied and socially significant research, especially in discourse analysis, sociolinguistics, and second language acquisition. The research also reveals such crucial challenges as the lack of access to research resources, insufficient supervision, and research design and methodology challenges.

The study is a valuable contribution to the current literature because it presents region-specific evidence on the practices of postgraduate research, which has been insufficiently studied in South Punjab. It also provides an integrated review of research domains, research methods and challenges, which can assist universities to better meet the research requirements of students.

The implications of the findings are also practical in nature as they propose university enhance the availability of research resources, offer systematic training in research methods, and enhance supervisory support. To enhance

the generalizability of studies on postgraduate research development and to draw comparative information on the subject, it is suggested that research involve larger sample sizes and a greater number of universities in different regions in the future.

Recommendations

According to the results, universities in South Punjab are advised to offer more access to research journals and online databases because many students have limited resources. It is necessary to introduce regular workshops devoted to research methods, data analysis, and academic writing to enhance the research abilities of the students. Supervisors should provide regular support and feedback that will encourage students to remain motivated and deliver their work on time. Opportunities for research collaboration in universities should be established, and small research grants or funding support may be given to students to promote innovation and productivity. These measures can be used to enhance the quality of postgraduate research in the field of linguistics as well as to establish a culture of research in the area.

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